
Comparative Analysis of the Pharmacological Attributes of *Moringa Oleifera* and *Acacia Nilotica*

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Abstract Series of research carried out in the area of pharmacognosy has led to identification of numerous medicinal plants. *Moringa oleifera* and *Acacia nilotica* are two highly nutritive plants with vast pharmacological properties. These plants are abundantly available in virtually all tropical and some sub-tropical countries. The medicinal properties of these two plants have not been fully studied in detail, hence, utilizing their full potentials in the main stream global orthodox medication is far from been achieved. In this review, we have put together a host of pharmacological activities of both plants, while analyzing their comparative advantages of their respective properties. Their medicinal properties include: anti-ulcer, anti-inflammatory, anti-epileptic, anti-bacterial, Analgesic, hepatoprotective, to mention a few. Also highlighted are the various parts of the plants namely leaves, stem, bark, root and their corresponding pharmacological properties providing interested researchers with useful information regarding the specific pharmacological activities elicited by extracts of the various parts. In conclusion, both *Moringa oleifera* and *Acacia nilotica* are suggested to possess similar pharmacological activities.

Keywords *Moringa oleifera*, *Acacia nilotica*, Plants, Medicinal, pharmacological, Ethnomedical

Introduction

Moringa oleifera, Lam syn. *M. pterygosperma*, Gaertn (Family – Moringaceae), is a small or medium-sized tree, attractive enough to be a focal point in the tropics and sub-tropics owing to its creamy – white, sweetly scented flowers and light-green, tripinnately compound foliage [1-3]. It is native to India, occurring wild in the sub-Himalayan regions of Northern India and cultivated throughout the country. It is commonly known as Sajina, sajna (Bengali); Horseradish tree, drumstick tree(English); Sahinjan, mungna(Hindi); Murinna, muringa, tishnagandha (Malyalam); Sevaga, segata (Marathi); Sohanjana (Punjabi); Sobhanjana, sigru, murungi, dvishiguru (Sanskrit) and Sehjan(Urdu) in varied Indian languages and regions [4-5]. It also thrives well in Pakistan, Bangladesh, Sri Lanka, tropical Africa, Arabia, Philippines, Cambodia and Central, North and South America [6-8].

Acacia nilotica Lam (Mimosaceae) indigenously known as 'Babul' or 'Kikar' is a proverbial, medium sized tree and is broadly scattered in tropical and subtropical countries. It has an inspiring range of medicinal uses with potential anti-oxidant activity. This plant contributes a number of groups among which are alkaloids, volatile essential oils, phenols and phenolic glycosides, resins, oleosins, steroids, tannins and terpenes. *A. nilotica* is a medicinal plant acknowledged to be rich in phenolics, consisting of condensed tannin and phlobatannin, gallic acid, protocatechuic acid, pyrocatechol, (+) -catechin, (-) epi- gallo catechin-7-gallate and (-) epigallocatechin-5, 7-digallate. Different parts of this plant such as the leaves, roots, seeds, bark, fruits, flowers, gum and immature pods act as anti-cancer, antimutagenic, spasmogenic, vasoconstrictor, anti-pyretic, anti-asthmatic, cytotoxic, anti-diabetic, anti-platelet aggregatory, anti-plasmodial, molluscicidal, anti-fungal, inhibitory activity against Hepatitis C virus (HCV) and human immunodeficiency virus (HIV)-I and antioxidant activities, anti-bacterial, anti-hypertensive and anti-spasmodic activities, and are also engaged for the treatment of different ailments in the indigenous system of medicine [9].

The medicinal and pharmacological activities of these plants include among others;

1. **Antipyretic Activity;** The ethanolic extract of *Moringa oleifera* has a significant antipyretic effect on human body. A research conducted by [10] showed that at doses of 100mg/kg body weight, extract of *Moringa oleifera* caused a significant lowering of body temperature.
2. **Anti-bacterial activity;** Antimicrobial multi-resistant bacterial strains are a growing public health concern worldwide, and the search for alternative forms of treating infections induced by such bacterial pathogens has become a focus of many researchers. The ethanolic extract of *Moringa oleifera* efficiently inhibit the growth of *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Vibrio cholera*, and *Escherichia coli* isolated from shrimp samples.
3. **Anti-asthmatic activity;** *Moringa oleifera* has been reported by many research groups to have antiasthmatic effect. A research conducted by Agarwal and Mehta showed that the efficacy and safety of seeds kernels of *Moringa oleifera* in treatment of bronchial asthma greatly increases with no adverse effect. *Moringa oleifera* also possess some beneficial properties that act against chemically stimulated immune-mediated inflammatory responses that are characteristics of asthma in rat [11].
4. **Anti-inflammatory activity;** *Moringa oleifera* plant has substantial anti-inflammatory activity. It was found by Mehyan and colleagues [12] that n-butanol extract of *Moringa oleifera* seeds shows anti-inflammatory activity against ovalbumin-induced air way inflammation in guinea pigs. Contrary to *M. oleifera*, *A. nilotica* lacks anti-inflammatory activity, this was established when *A. nilotica* extract was administered in rats with egg albumin induced inflammatory edema. Absence of paw edema suppression indicates lack of anti- inflammatory activity [13].
5. **Analgesic activity;** The leaves and seed extracts of *M. oleifera* possess a marked analgesic activity as experimentally revealed in a hot plate and tail immersion method [14]. Analgesic activity of *A. nilotica* tested against acid induced pain in rat also reveals high percentages of analgesia [15].
6. **Hypocholesterolemic activity;** Methanolic extracts of *M. oleifera* was found to contain some alkaloids whose weekly moderate dose level treatment in mice change serum aminotransferase and plasma cholesterol level significantly [16].
7. **Wound healing;** The ethyl acetate extract of fresh and dried leaves of *M. oleifera* is reported to possess significant wound healing potentials. Bioactive fraction of *M. oleifera* containing Vicenin-2 compound enhances faster wound healing [17]. Also, the ethanolic extract of *A. nilotica* exhibit marked wound healing activity and significantly enhance the wound contraction and the period of epithelialization.
8. **Hepatoprotective activity;** The leaves and ethanol extracts of *M. oleifera* showed significant protection against liver damage induced by anti-tubercular drugs in rats [18]. Various studies reported the ethanolic extract of *M. oleifera* seeds and leaves to possess hepatoprotective reaction [19-20]. The root and flower extracts also showed antihepatotoxic activity [21]. Remarkable protective effect has been observed against CCl₄ – induced liver fibrosis in rats [21].
9. **Antispasmodic activity;** The root and leaves of *M. oleifera* contains several compound with spasmodic activity. The spasmolytic activity of the different constituents support for traditional uses of this plant in gastrointestinal motility disorder [22]. *A. nilotica* was found to have spasmodic activity on isolated guinea pig ileum [15].
10. **Antiulcer activity;** Wide spectrum pharmacological properties of *M. oleifera* as a versatile medicinal plant, includes its potent antiulcer activity. A research conducted by Debnath and Guha [23] reported the antiulcer effect of *M. oleifera* leaves aqueous extracts on adult Holtzman albino rats. The methanolic flower bud extract of *M. oleifera* also showed a decrease in ulcer index of aspirin-induced gastric ulcer in rats [24]. The leaf extract of *M. oleifera* also produced a significant reduction of stress-induced ulcers and cysteamine-induced duodenal ulcers. However, *A. nilotica* reportedly demonstrated a significant antiulcer activity in pyloric ligation, swimming stress and induced rat ulcer model [25].
11. **Anti-hyperglycemic effect;** An *in vivo* research [26] showed that 20mgkg⁻¹ dose of aqueous extracts of *M. oleifera* significantly reduce urine sugar and urine protein level in mice.
12. **Anti-diabetic;** Several medicinal plants including *M. oleifera* have been evaluated for their potentials as therapeutic agents for diabetes. The leaves of *M. oleifera* significantly decrease blood glucose concentration in Wistar rat and Goto-Kakizaki (GK) rats, modeled type 2 diabetes [27]. *A. nilotica* pods and tender leaves are also considered very beneficial in folk medicine to treat diabetes mellitus [28].
13. **Anti-tumor;** *M. oleifera* is a potent anticancer plant and several bioactive compounds with significant antitumor activity have been discovered from *M. oleifera*. Among bioactive compounds from *M.*

- oleifera*, niazimicin, a *M. oleifera* leaves thiocarbamate was found to have potent anticancer activity [29-30]. Beside leaves, *M. oleifera* seed extracts also have anticancer activity through its effect on hepatic carcinogen metabolizing enzyme [31]. *A. nilotica* has been reported to have chemoprotective and anti-mutagenic activity [33].
14. **Anti-plasmodia;** In vitro studies have depicted anti-protozoal effect of *M. oleifera*. Soluble lectin from the seed extract of *M. oleifera* was found to show larvicidal activity by delaying larval development and promoting mortality in *Aedes aegypti* possibly on account of its hemagglutinating activity [32]. The root extract of *A. nilotica* was found to have significant anti-plasmodic against chlorine sensitive strain of *Plasmodium bergheri* in mice [33].
 15. **Antioxidant;** Exploration of *M. oleifera* as a potential source of antioxidants has yielded affirmative results [34]. The aqueous extracts of leaf, fruit and seed of *M. oleifera* act as an antioxidants [35]. Also, the bark powder of *A. nilotica* is known to have antioxidant activity. A study by Amos and colleagues [36], reveals that *A. nilotica* is easily accessible source of natural antioxidants which can be used as a supplement to aid the therapy of free-radicals mediated diseases such as cancer, diabetes, inflammation and ,many more pathological disorders..
 16. **Anti-peroxidative;** The phenolic contents present in the leaves of *M. oleifera* imparts free-radicals scavenging property while the ethanolic fraction showed considerable metal chelation properties with potentials to protect against DNA nicking [37].
 17. **Anti-hypertensive;** *M. oleifera* leaf juice has been found to exert a stabilizing effect on blood pressure. The leaves of *M. oleifera* also contain bioactive compounds which exert direct effect on blood pressure and thus this can be used for stabilizing blood pressure [18]. A decrease in arterial blood pressure has been reported by use of methanolic extracts of *A. nilotica* pods and provides evidence of muscarinic receptor stimulation [18].
 18. **Cardioprotective;** Lyophilized hydroalcoholic extracts of *M. oleifera* was found to show myocardial preservatives effect in isoproterenol (ISP)-induced model of myocardial infraction [38].
 19. **Central Nervous System (CNS) Activities;** Chronic oral treatment of ethanolic extract of *M. oleifera* leaves were found to alter the brain monoamines in distinct areas of brain in rat model of Alzheimer's disease caused by intracerebral vertical (ICV) infusion of colchine and hence provide protection against monoaminergic defects associated with Alzheimer [39]. Protection against strychnine and leptazol-induced convulsion was also observed on pretreatment with methanolic root extract including a dose dependent CNS depressant effect [40,41,42].
 20. **Cardiac activity;** Histopathological findings of mycordial tissues have shown the protective role of *M. oleifera* in isoproterenol(ISO)-induced cardio toxicity. The stem bark of *M. oleifera* has been found to have prophylactic cardioprotective effect, and the leave extracts displayed hypolipidemic and antioxidant effect in ISO-induced cardiotoxicity [45].

Summary of documented research on Medicinal and Pharmacological properties of *Moringa oleifera* (MO) AND *Acacia nilotica* (AN)

S/n	Activities	Mo	An	Source in mo	Source in an	Extract	Reference
1	Anti-pyretic	✓	✓	Seed	Gum	Ethanolic(MO)	10, 42, 43
2	Anti-asthmatic	✓	✓	Seeds	Gum	Ethanolic (MO)	1, 44
3	Anti-inflammatory	✓	✓	Root	Tender leaves		45, 46
4	Anti-arthritis	✓		Root			44
5	Anti-analgesic	✓	✓	Root	Plant	Methanolic and Alcoholic (MO),extract(A N)	44, 47, 48
6	Hypocholesterotemic	✓		Leaf			8, 49, 50
7	Wound healing	✓		Leaves		Aqueous	51, 52
8	Anti-thyroid	✓		Leaves		Just extract	44, 53

9	Anti-microbial	✓	✓	Leaf, seed, Leaf and root, stem, stem back		Aqueous extract of seeds(MO), ethanolic(AN)	3, 44, 54, 55, 56, 57, 58, 59, 60
10	Anti-anaphylactic	✓		Seeds		Ethanolic	60
11	Hepato-protective	✓		Seeds and leaves		Ethanolic	44, 61, 62, 63 64, 65
12	Anti-hepatotoxic	✓		Root and flower		Just extract	61, 63, 64,
13	Radio-protective	✓		Leaves		Methanolic	44, 66
14	Anti-ulcer	✓		Flower bud		Methanolic	45, 51, 55
15	Anti-spasmodic	✓	✓	Roots and leaves	Plant	Ethanolic extract of leaves(MO), methanolic(AN)	44, 67, 68, 102
16	Anti-hyperglycemic	✓		Leaf		Aqueous	44, 69,
17	Anti-diabetic	✓	✓	Leaf	Pods &tender leaves	Aqueous(MO)	69, 70
18	Anti-tumor	✓	✓	Leaves	Root	Ethanolic(MO)	71, 72, 73
19	Chemo-protective	✓	✓	Leaves	Leaf flower	Leaf extract(AN)	61, 73
20	Anti-proliferative	✓		Plant			44, 72, 74, 75
21	Anti- plasmodia			Seed	Root	Just extract(mo),acetate methanolic(AN)	13, 76, 77, 116
22	Anti-progestational	✓	✓	Roots		Aqueous	44, 78, 79, 80
23	Anti-implantational characteristic	✓		Roots		Aqueous	78, 82
24	Anti-oxidant	✓	✓	Leaves	Plant	Methanolic	1, 30, 44, 83, 84, 85, 86,
25	Anti-peroxidative	✓		Seed		Ethanolic,seed powder	9, 87, 88, 89, 90,
26	Diuretic			Seeds, leaves, flowers, gums, root	Gum	Aqueous infusion os seeds(MO)	44, 91
27	Antiuro lithiatic	✓	✓	Root-wood		Alcoholic	91
28	Anti-hypertensive	✓	✓	Leaves and pods	Pods	Leaf juice and ethanolic(MO), methanolic (AN)	8, 9, 68, 92, 93, 94 , 95, 96, 97
29	Cardio-protective	✓		Leaves		Lyophilized hydroalcoholic	73
30	CNS activities	✓		Leaves		Ethanolic	98, 99
31	Cardiac and	✓		Root back,		Just extract	44

32	circulatory stimulant Anti-bacterial		✓	leaves	Leaf	Methanolic	44, 88, 89,100
33	Anti-fungal	✓	✓	Plant	Dried fruit	Methanolic and aqueous	44,101,102, 103, 104
34	Anti-viral		✓			Methanolic	105
35	Anti-biotic		✓		Plant	Just extract	56, 106
36	Anti-malaria		✓		Root	Extract, crude methanolic	13,
37	Anti-diarrhea		✓		Bark	Powdered bark, infusion	44, 107
38	Spasmogenic		✓		Seeds	Aqueous	92, 93, 94
39	Molluscicidal properties		✓		Stem bark and fruit	Acetone, alcohol and aqueous	44, 108, 109
40	Vasoconstriction		✓		Plant	Aqueous	8, 44
41	Anti-mutagenic		✓		Leaf and gum	Acetone	75
42	Cytotoxic		✓		Plant	Acetone	110
43	Anti- hepatocarcinogenic		✓		Bark	Extract	63
44	Anthelmintic		✓		Fruit and gum	Methanolic	110
45	Milk production		✓		Plant	Aqueous	112
46	Antiplatelet aggregatory		✓		Plant	Extract	113
47	Anti-cancer		✓		Root		76, 114
48	Astringent		✓		Gum and leaf		44
49	Aphrodisiac		✓		Gum and tender leaves		44
50	ulcer dressing / hemorrhagic ulcer wounds		✓		Tender leaves	Decoction of leaves	103
51	Liver tonic		✓		Gum		
52	Anti dysentery		✓		Stem bark &gum		44, 113
53	Antifertility	✓	✓	Root and bark	Pods	Aqueous extract (mo)	113
54	Mild laxative		✓		Leaf, fruit & seed		115, 116
55	Nutritive tonic		✓		Gum		115, 116
56	Gingivitis		✓		Gum		44

57	Expectorant	✓	Gum and pods	113
58	Demulcent	✓	Gum	44, 113
59	Piles, vaginitis and cystitis	✓	Bark	Decoction of bark
60	Gonorrhoea	✓	Tender growing tops	Aqueous 113
61	Hemorrhagic ulcer wounds	✓	Leaves	Decoction of leaves 103
62	Antiseptic	✓	Plant	48
63	Decongestant	✓	Plant	107, 113

Future Perspective

The ethno medical uses of this two plants cited in several scientific researches, has unveiled their wide spectrum of pharmacological properties. Most research conducted on these plants, are focused on identification and evaluation of their pharmacological activities through *in vitro* and *in vivo* study. Therefore, Emphasis should be placed on towards conducting clinical trials, which will eventually result in establishment of standard drugs obtainable from various parts of these plants, which can be safely administered for therapeutic purposes. It is also recommended to leverage on the high nutritive values of the plants by making it part of the dietary intake, while taking into consideration the appropriate quantity safe for consumption and also the consumers health status. Furthermore, despite their nutritive values, some patients under a particular medication might elicit adverse reaction when taken concurrently with such medications and might as well be out rightly contraindicated in certain group of candidates who do not well tolerate the use of the plants. Conventional treatments of conditions like cancer, employs chemotherapy and radiation therapy, which are often accompanied by series of adverse effects, hence, use ethno medical products such as *Moringa oleifera* and *Acacia nolitica* with little or no adverse effects, would be of great importance. It is highly recommended that more research be conducted to evaluate the combine effects of these plants, perhaps this could be more beneficial.

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